
National information system platforms (NISP) to support decision making in ST&I policies: Brazilian NISP analysis and perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Science, Technology and Innovation (ST&I) are acknowledged as essential for socioeconomic development. However, measuring the impact of public investment in those fields is still a challenge. One of the resources to evaluate ST&I is data collected by the information systems dedicated to support funding and other key processes in the National Innovation System (NIS). Those systems are called Current Research Information Systems (CRIS), systems that manage ST&I data in several processes (e.g., data collection, proposal evaluation and project tracking). In the last decades, CRIS have enabled governments to better manage processes such as funding and evaluation. However, the existence of CRIS data per se is not a guarantee of data availability for strategic decision making, such as assessing impact of ST&I investments. This is particularly critical when the analyses are about national (or regional) innovation systems, because data must represent activities of multiple stakeholders. When CRIS are developed without a national strategy for ST&I information, it will be difficult to establish relationships, cause-effect studies, and other analyses that support strategic decision making. In a national scenario, a set of information systems is referred to as National Information System Platform (NISP). In the last fifteen years Brazil has created several NISP in ST&I, based on an e-Gov methodology and architecture that support both operational processes and strategic decision making. National ST&I information such as *Plataforma Lattes* (CNPq), *Portal Inovação* (MCT/CGEE) and *Portal SINAES* (INEP/MEC) were developed according to this e-Gov methodology. In this article we present such methodology and its application in some of the most important Brazilian ST&I NISP. We discuss some of the lessons learned from these projects and their guidelines to create ST&I data useful to strategic decision making.

INTRODUCTION

In the last thirty years, public managers became increasingly aware of the relevance of having current and accurate information to support decision making. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) are among the main resources to do so. As a consequence, modern Information and Communication Technology heavily impacts and shapes government activities for cooperating and interacting with stakeholders (i.e., citizens, citizen groups, NGOs society, businesses, and other government agencies within and across borders). This ICT evolution is characterized by a so called bottom-up approach: information systems are initially dedicated to support operational processes and latter their transactional data is transformed to support decision making. Generally this approach reveals an information gap since the original requirements were not related to problems of strategic decision making.

In the case of Science, Technology and Innovation (ST&I) the systems are created mainly to help funding agencies in bid for ST&I grants, to evaluate proposals and to follow projects. In such processes researchers usually fill in data about their personal profile, research team and project identification, attaching a document with a detailed research proposal. These data are suitable for evaluation and other operational processes. When it comes to analyzing impacts, however, the public administrator faces the lack of appropriate information, shortcoming that is worse when the analysis involves multiple agencies or even multiple grants.

In the last fifteen years Brazilian ST&I governmental information systems have been following a systemic view of ST&I information. The first set of CRIS was *Plataforma Lattes*, created by the Brazilian National Council on S&T – CNPq, in a joint project with academic groups. These groups developed a new e-Gov methodology applied in different information architectures: *Portal Inovação* (from MCT - Ministry of Science and Technology), *National Competence Directory* (from ANVISA - National Health Surveillance Agency), and others. The databases created in these projects have helped the analysis of ST&I evaluation and planning.

In this article we revisit history, principles, and main guidelines of the Brazilian e-Gov methodology to create ST&I information platforms. The purpose is to discuss how this methodology can take ST&I information systems beyond operational data. We also discuss how such guidelines can help public managers to demand national information systems that contribute not only to the funding and proposal evaluation processes but also in establishing a background for strategic analyses such as foresight, impact evaluation and expertise location. We also discuss how such systems should be influenced by the new possibilities of social networks and by knowledge society mechanisms.

SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION SYSTEMS

ST&I information systems result from software applications that help automate processes related to one or more innovation player. Such processes are institutional, geographic, and thematic located. In the institutional aspect, a process must have defined the organizational and procedural stages where information is needed (e.g., in a funding agency: public call for proposals, proposal evaluation, project reporting). Regarding geography, an information system can be local, regional, national or international. As for the thematic aspect the systems can be applied to wide or to particular contexts (e.g., national curriculum system or particular funding process electronic form). Besides, information systems are related to different ST&I players, including data requester and supplier.

This complex set of components requires an integrated view of the wide system affected by the information systems. This means that before establishing software requirements, the software engineer should be concerned about the conceptual view supporting the processes. In ST&I such conceptual views are proposed by researchers and organizations dedicated to understand processes, players, mechanisms, structures and other issues related to knowledge and innovation.

In this section, we briefly describe three conceptual approaches to identify players and their relationships in an innovation system.

ST&I conceptual frameworks

A ST&I conceptual framework is a schematic view of a National Innovation System. **A National Innovation Systems (NIS)** is “the system of interacting private and public **firms** (either large or small), **universities**, and **government agencies** aiming at the production of science and technology within national borders. Interaction among these units may be technical,

commercial, legal, social, and financial, in as much as the goal of the interaction is the development, protection, financing or regulation of new science and technology” (Niosi et al., 1993).

The main players in a science, technology and innovation system are firms, universities and government agencies. Identifying the players and their role is the first step to establish an integrated view of information processes. The next task is to establish a schematic view of how they connect and interact with each other. A suitable way of establishing such view is to consider conceptual frameworks created to analyze the innovation systems. In the case of ST&I systems, there are linear and nonlinear views of how players and relationships interact.

The classic linear model of innovation was conceived after Second World War. In synthesis, according to the linear framework innovation is an indirect result of applied science. The concept was based on the experience of some countries. It states that basic research leads to applied research which leads to knowledge creation and consequently to practical applications that will fund basic research (Nilsson, et. al. 2003). This assumption could not explain real major technologic developments and was later replaced by nonlinear models. Nonlinear frameworks recognize the fact that knowledge production transcends organizational boundaries established by each innovation player role (Nilsson, et al. 2003).

In Figure 1 we illustrate three conceptual frameworks with a nonlinear view of the ST&I players and relationships.

Figure 1: three nonlinear conceptual framework for national innovation systems

The first model in Figure 1 was proposed by Jorge Sábato and Natalio Botana (Sábato and Botana, 1968). They proposed a paradigm shift to recognize the role of science and technology in the Latin American social and economic development. Their work emphasized the impact of S&T on the country capacity of technology creation and absorption, intelligent use of natural resources, and social change. Their view was denoted by an articulated scheme of three vertices: government, universities and firms. The model describes intra, inter and extra-

relations among those players that form the national ST&I system capacity. In this view government plays a central role establishing and conducting the S&T policy. Universities and similar institutions offer the scientific and technological infrastructure and firms establish the demand for technology and human resources. This dynamics is known as Sabato's triangle.

The second nonlinear conceptual framework to describe innovation was developed by Loet Leydesdorff e Henry Etzkowitz (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000). It is called the Triple Helix model and it also emphasizes the three essential players and their communication networks (Leydesdorff, 2000). Each player is seen as a helix representing at the same time the dynamic nature of its innovation role and the interaction with the other two in the process of knowledge production. This model considers the multiple factors involved in innovation and social development in communication, geographic, economy, market, policy, organizational and social dimensions. The model also recognizes the internal transformation of each helix, the influence of one helix upon another, the existence of trilateral networks and organizations from the interaction among the helices and the effect of these networks on the knowledge base of the innovation system (Nilsson, et al., 2003).

The third model represented in Figure 1 was proposed by the Organization for Economic and Cooperation Development - OECD (OECD, 1997) to study and compare national innovation systems. The model proposes a framework with innovation players involved in knowledge creation, diffusion and use (including the different forms of interaction). Similarly to the Sabato's and Triple Helix models, the OECD's systemic model has industry, government and ST&I institutions as the main innovation players. However, the model adds individuals (researchers) and other kinds of organizations (such as innovation agencies), and makes it explicit the collective arrangements among players (clusters, research groups, networks). These players are subject to five macro factors that influence the national innovation capacity: macroeconomic and regulatory environment, communication infrastructure, educational and training system, and two kinds of market conditions: products and factors. The model emphasizes the economic and social role of investment in knowledge.

The three conceptual frameworks identify innovation players and the main factors that influence their dynamics in a national ST&I setting. These elements are crucial to ST&I information projects. In this sense a conceptual framework works as a reference to reveal how each data requirement impacts (and is impacted by) the dynamics of the innovation players. In practice, when a public manager decides to create an electronic form to collect data in a particular process (for instance, in a public call for proposals), this decision will impact the national information system (with possible redundancy, fragmentation, integration, imposed delays, rework, rationalization, automation, etc.).

In the next section we analyze the ST&I players, processes and data as concerns for information system design.

Main ST&I players, processes and data

Innovation players are involved in a series of processes such as planning, funding, evaluation assessment, control, and ST&I diffusion. These ST&I processes are part of a bigger set of management responsibilities. In Figure 2 we represent the set of players, processes, tasks, and data usually related to ST&I funding.

Figure 2: main processes, tasks and data requirements in ST&I funding.

Each phase of the funding processes represented in Figure 2 has different players, processes, tasks and data requirements.

In the planning phase, the public managers define priorities and resources that should be considered in the ST&I system. The planning stage establishes funding programs related to the funding agency mission (e.g., program to create new innovative companies in innovation agencies). In terms of data the planning stages deals with plans, decision reports and budgets. In democratic systems this phase should be taken into account the society demands for investments in ST&I.

The next step is to launch public calls for proposals in each of the funding programs defined by the agency. From the funding agency point of view, this phase requires public announcements, the publication of a term of reference and the preparation to deal with the demand – receive proposals, analyze the documents, etc. To the ST&I players, this phase is related to the preparation of funding candidates and proposal. During the public calls, the information systems include applications for managing proponent profiles (according to the kind of ST&I player), proposal registering and the document reception and analysis.

The third phase in the funding process is related to proposal evaluation. Usually, the funding agencies invite specialists in the area of the funding program and ask them for a peer review

evaluation. Proposals are then classified according to the candidate profile, project quality, and budget adequacy to the funding program goals.

In the next phase, the funding agency representatives will proceed with the analysis of the classified proposals in order to prepare the research contract. Issues such as document analysis, institutional agreements, work plan analysis, and budget adjustments can take place during this phase.

There is need to manage the evolution of project contracts from both sides – the agency and the funding beneficiary – after it is signed. During these periods, the beneficiary will be conducting the research, producing results and partial reports, and informing the agency about such evolutions, as well as about the project financial workflow. To deal with this information, the agencies usually apply a control system while project leaders use project management tools. As represented in Figure 2, the project products in this phase are similar to the ones produced in the end of the project (including training of undergraduate and graduate students).

Finally, the last stage is the conclusion of the funding process. This includes the final project report and it might involve project assessment studies. During the last periods of the project, the beneficiaries usually announce their results in seminars and events. The project results are among the most important data and they come from a variety of sources.

In terms of a national ST&I information system, funding processes are among the most important. They establish a continuous basis for data creation, collection, and exploitation. The most decentralized is the ST&I system, the most diverse will be the available information systems. With time, there will be a collection of data sources, with redundant and fragmented information. Although each individual agency can keep its data to support its mission, the ST&I system as a whole will lack aggregated information to answer questions on the national R&D capabilities, investment impacts, and trends.

This does not mean that there is need for a unique national technological platform. The problem is related to the lack of standards and to isolated information systems. In the next section, we present the main general ST&I information entities that should be standardized so all funding agencies and other ST&I players could adopt those standards in information system initiatives.

General ST&I information entities

An information entity is a piece of process (business) data with a unique semantic definition. As such, an information entity should have its content agreed among the players involved. Ideally its name, content and use should be references to current and future information systems developed in the same domain.

There have been a number of initiatives to establish information entities in ST&I. The most well known are the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF), established by the European Committee of Current Information System (CORDIS, 1991), and the Dublin Core, created in 1995 to establish interoperable metadata standards (Greenberg, 2010). In Latin

American, there is also the ScienTI Network, created to establish common standards and systems to ST&I, based on the Brazilian experience of Plataforma Lattes (Pacheco, et. al., 2006; Sartori and Pacheco, 2006).

By analyzing these standards and comparing different projects in ST&I information systems we can identify a common set of information entities. In Table 1 we list the main information entities found in ST&I information systems.

Table 1 – Main ST&I information entities

Info Type	ST&I Information Entity	Description	Main Data fields
I	Curriculum	Structural (and non redundant) data about individual, personal, and professional profiles of researchers, students, and other professionals involved in ST&I.	Identification, addresses, education background, honors, publications, theses and dissertations, (non) registered technical production (software, products, processes), professional experiences (projects, institutional affiliations), relationships (advising, collaborations, etc).
I	Web profile	Unstructured (and redundant) data about the individual, available in the Web. It is also suitable for automatic populate other information system sources.	Homepage, references, publications, news, images, social network participations, events, etc.
I or C	Project proposal	Structured and documental data with information about the funding candidate(s), the project and expected results.	Project title, abstract, research areas, keywords, project team, work plan, budget, funding (financial agency, fund program, requirements, etc), project impact.
C	Project team	Structured data about the project teams (individuals that work together in a project during a certain period of time).	Each team individual identification, team profile, institutional links, project.
C	Research group	Structured data about a group of researchers and students (individuals sharing infrastructure and R&D lines of work).	Group title, description, institutional affiliations, research areas, keywords, research team (researchers, technicians and students), group projects, and partners.
C	R&D networks	Structured and unstructured data about research networks.	Network identification, purposes, components, homepage, main projects.
O	ISTI (and its organizational units)	Structured data about an Institution of Science, Technology and Innovation (universities, research institutes, research centers) and its units (departments, labs).	ISTI identification, personnel (professors, students, employees), organizational structure (departments, laboratories, etc), and R&D Infrastructure (equipments, facilities).
O	Courses	Structured data about undergraduate and graduate courses	Identification (name, area), personnel (students, professors, technicians, alumni), academic structure and outputs (curricula, theses and dissertations), and R&D outputs (publications).
O	Public agencies	Structured data about the public organizations that plan, fund, evaluate, and promote ST&I	Agency identification, personnel, plans, programs, instruments, budget, investments, and other actions related to ST&I promotion.
O	Firms	Structured data about industrial, technological and service firms in the ST&I system.	Firm identification, profile (economic sector, size, intellectual property), portfolio (products, services), funded projects, personnel profile, and stakeholders (partners, suppliers, clients).
O	Other organizations	Structured and non structured data about firm associations, incubators, S&T parks, academic societies, private associations, NGOs and other organizations involved in ST&I (including editors and event promoters)	Organization identification and ST&I portfolio (including the ST&I players to which the organization mission is dedicated)
I, C or O	Innovation demands or offerings	Structured and non structured data about ST&I players demands and offerings - what they need or offer as innovation players.	Demand/offering type (e.g., technical support, personnel capacitation, exporting support, importing replacement, other), and area (process, infrastructure, services and solutions, technology diffusion, product, basic industrial technology, planning and management, other).

I – Data about individuals; C – data about a collective; O – data about an organization.

In a national view of information in ST&I the entities reported in Table 1 keep a variety of relationships among them. These relations form a ST&I data net in which a link represents a reference from one entity to another. In a CV system, for instance, the professional address can link the individual to organizations, an education background relates a person to an educational institution, and so on. In Figure 3 we represent relations of the most connected entity – the individual curriculum.

Figure 3: ST&I data net: relationships between CVs and other ST&I entities.

The dotted lines in Figure 3 represent loose connections between a cv and another entity while the bold lines indicate structured (uniquely identified) connections between the individual cv and the another entity. An example in the first case is the line between a cv and a project proposal document. The second entity can mention the author or team, but only by name and organization (which makes it difficult to identify univocally the project authorship). On the other hand the connection between a CV and a project proposal description indicates that in the second entity the information systems are structured and can connect authors with undoubtful identity.

In order to have an integrated view of the ST&I information systems, the projects should respect standards on the data described in Table 1, and make use of interoperability services to avoid data redundancy. This would establish a ST&I national information system platform. As we see in the next section, such information systems platforms respect individual organization processes but at the same time create and maintain information to support decisions for the benefit of the entire innovation system.

NATIONAL INFORMATION VIEWS

In this section we present the concept of a National Information System Platform (NISP) and its correspondent in ST&I – Current Research Information Systems (CRIS). These acronyms represent different views of national information platforms. The first is a generic concept that can be applied to different areas (e.g., NISP in Health, NISP in Environment, etc.) and the second is the NISP in ST&I fields.

These concepts are particularly relevant when one is establishing information systems that interfere/interact with different players related to a field. In this article they will be a reference to discuss some guidelines and requirements that should be observed in national information platforms in ST&I, particularly when the goals include the support to strategic decision making.

National Information System Platform - NISP

A **National Information Systems Platform (NISP)** was first realized as a “‘a coherent array’ of information subsystems with the capacity to intercommunicate” (Aines, 1968). By “coherent” the first NISP conception already meant that there were different features for its components.

A NISP is not an ultimate centralized computerized information system. Its main purpose is to define guidelines and requirements that work as a reference to software engineers. The concept “platform” means a set of components that together form a whole of information sources. The essential element in national information platforms is not the computing but the ability of establishing the managerial mission of the systems.

This NISP characteristic has already been acknowledged for a long time, either in specific areas such as repository information retrieval systems - where planning is considered more important than computing (Lytle, 1978) or in the own national information system studies - where mission-oriented systems are considered more important than function-oriented systems (Polinière, 1975).

NISP as an e-Gov solution

Even though NISP is not only a matter of public systems, government is one of the main players since it is the one in best position to establish official national systems. In this sense, NISP is related to **electronic government (e-Gov)**. The concept of e-Gov has been proposed by several researchers and organizations. In Table 2 we present the most known concepts adopted by international organizations.

Table 2 – Main e-Gov definitions

e-Gov Initiative	e-Gov concept adopted
European Information Technology Observatory (European Information Technology Observatory (EITO), 2002, p. 288)	e-Gov is defined as the use of Internet technologies to conduct, enhance and support relations with, and transactions between, different government bodies and citizens, businesses and other government bodies.
World Bank	e-Gov refers to the use by government agencies of information technologies (such as wide area networks, the internet, and mobile computing) that have the ability to transform relations with citizens, businesses, and other arms of government. These technologies can serve a variety of different ends: better delivery of government services to citizens, improved interactions with business and industry, citizen empowerment through access to information, or more efficient government management. The resulting benefits can be less corruption, increased transparency, greater convenience, revenue growth, and/or cost reductions.
OECD	The use of information and communication technologies, and particularly the Internet, as a tool to achieve better government.
Pacific Council on International Policy, Working Group on e-Gov in the Developing World	e-Gov is the use of ICT to promote more efficient and effective government, facilitate more accessible government services, allow greater public access to information, and make government more accountable to citizens. e-Gov might involve delivering services via the Internet, telephone, community centers (self-service or facilitated by others), wireless devices or other communications systems.
United Nations	e-Gov is defined as utilizing the Internet and the worldwide-web for delivering government information and services to citizens.
Gartner Group	The continuous optimization of service delivery, constituency participation, and governance by transforming internal and external relationships through technology, the Internet, and new media.

As we can see from Table 2, there is no consensus about a unique definition of e-Gov (Pacheco, et. al. 2007). However, the concept is related to the application of information and communication technologies to support government activities.

For some public managers, the ultimate e-Gov goal is to establish a “computerization of administrative systems that takes care of everything through the internal affair connection.” (Jung-hyup, 2010).

This view represents well the first generation of e-Gov solutions, in which the main target was to apply ICT to improve government performance, based mainly on internal processes. However, a more updated view puts e-Gov as an instrument to establish a virtuous relationship between government and society. Electronic government is the use of internet and information technologies to simplify or improve the way citizens, public employees, partners and other organizations interact with government and conduct business (Koh et. al, 2005).

This view is in accordance with the OECD perception of the relevance of e-Gov to improve public efficiency, services, help in particular policy outcomes (as education and training), and build trust between government and citizens (OECD, 2003). The OECD proposes ten guidelines for a successful e-Gov approach (Figure 4).

Figure 4: the OECD guidelines principles for successful e-Gov (based on OECD, 2003).

The OECD studies conclude that a successful e-Gov approach is based on the following: (a) adequate political view/will; (b) common cooperation framework; (c) focus on the customer; and (d) public commitment with responsibility accountability and evaluation. In this view, e-Gov is an enabler not an end itself and its project should be based on broader policies and service goals (OECD, 2003). The efforts should be orchestrated among agencies based on interoperability, efficiency and duplication avoidance. ICT is a crucial investment asset (not a cost item) and there should be a program fund to foster innovation (OECD, 2003).

By focusing on the customer an e-Gov project should: (i) pursue access to online services, (ii) allow different choices when access government services, (iii) provide high quality services and citizen engagement with appropriate information provision and strengthening of citizen participation; and (iv) protect individual privacy. Regarding responsibility e-gov projects should make clear who is responsible for shared projects and initiatives and assure that private sector participation does not reduce accountability. They should also identify costs, benefits, and impacts of the e-Gov initiatives (OECD, 2003).

As we will see further, these guidelines are similar to the lessons learned in the Brazilian e-Gov projects on ST&I. In the last fourteen years, the conception of an e-Gov methodology and its application to several e-Gov architectures in ST&I confirmed the OECD guidelines as well as derived other conclusions on how such systems can be more cost effectively. These issues are treated in the next sections of this article.

But first, we address another concept that is important to understand the role of information systems in ST&I: CRIS - *Current Research Information Systems*. A CRIS is every information system that deals with ST&I data listed in Table 1. This includes for instance university legacy systems (e.g., course registration, human resource system), library information systems, and public funding information systems. In the next section we deal with CRIS concept and its state in Europe.

Current Information Research Systems – CRIS

The problem of managing research information was already tackled, long before internet era (Zimmerman, 2002). According to Skolnik (1967), in the middle 60s there were already about 300 information services for searching abstracts. Another example from this period is the work of the Smithsonian Science Information Exchange and UNESCO on an international standard taxonomy for fields of science and technology. Behind such taxonomy is the need to easily access information regarding ideas, technical reports, publications, patents, technical production, competences, R&D facilities, and other R&D data (Zimmerman, 2002).

A CRIS (Current Research Information System) is any information system used to manage structured or unstructured ST&I data. According to EUROCRIS, a “CRIS records the R&D activity either funded by or carried out by an organisation, or within a thematic or subject area. Typically it covers projects, people (expertise), organisational structure, R&D outputs (products, patents, publications), R&D events and R&D facilities and equipment.” (EUROCRIS, 2006).

In Europe, in order to establish standards to deal with research information a group of experts proposed CERIF – Common European Research Information Format. In 2002, an European Commission founded euroCRIS as a non for profit organization to deal with CRIS and to establish CERIF. In euroCRIS, a CRIS is considered “any informational tool dedicated to provide access to and disseminate research information. A CRIS consists of a data model describing objects of interest to R&D and a tool or set of tools to manage the data.” (EUROCRIS, 2011).

It is important to notice the switch on the way euroCRIS has been dealing with the problem of R&D data standards. According to its site “the time has come to abandon CRIS as data silos and develop or convert them in such a way that integration and interchange of research information including from/to other systems dealing with funding programmes, project management, projects, organisations, human resource management, people, patents, finance and publications is enabled – with CERIF as middle layer providing the interconnection and integration.” (EUROCRIS, 2011)¹.

This is the challenge ahead for all NISP in ST&I: rather than establishing a centralized research database, a R&D NISP should be developed as a result of mature e-Gov projects, that leave space for citizen participation and system interoperability. The issue behind such challenge is the view of e-Gov project that leads the R&D NISP project. In the next sections we describe a brief history of national CRIS developed in Brazil and the new possibilities that arise from the e-Gov view adopted in such projects .

¹ In practice this view represents that a national information system in ST&I has redundancy by definition. A comparison between CERIF and ScienTI (Lattes) model showed that while the first considers publications a separate database that should not replicate individual articles, ScienTI model treats articles as replicated record in each author’s CV (Pacheco, et. al., 2006). This happens because ScienTI model considers each relation author-article as an individual profile (e.g., the article keywords registered in each CV represent the way each author has contributed to the work and not the official keywords published with the article).

BRAZILIAN NATIONAL ST&I INFORMATION SYSTEM

As any other National Innovation System, the Brazilian NIS can be viewed as a set of different innovation players (firms, S&T organizations, government, and others) placed on an environment with several factors that influence their capacity of creating knowledge and wealth.

In Brazil, the scientific and academic sector has 2.314 higher education institutions² and more than 200 research organizations³. There are more 6,8 million of firms⁴ and several public organizations related to ST&I. In Table 1 we list the main Brazilian innovation players.

Innovation player	Examples
Firms	Petrobras, Embraer, Natura, Votorantin
IST	USP, Unicamp, UFRJ, UFRGS, UFSC, Embrapa, CENPES (Petrobras R&D Center)
Government	MCT, MEC, MDIC, CNPq, CAPES, FINEP, BNDES, FAPs
Other organizations	Firm associations (CNI, SEBRAE, SENAI, ANPROTEC); S&T associations (SBPC, ABC); ONGs (CGEE, RNP), IST association (ABIPTI), regulatory agencies (ANVISA, ANEEL)

In Figure 5 we illustrate the environment associated to some Brazilian innovation players and innovation factors.

Figure 5: Schematic view (examples) of the Brazilian National Innovation System
(based on Pacheco, et. al. 2010)

² Source: INEP – Instituto Nacional de Estudos e Pesquisas Educacionais Anísio Teixeira – Censo 2009 - <http://portal.inep.gov.br/superior-censosuperior-sinopse>

³ Total of associated institutions at the Associação Brasileira de Instituições de Pesquisa Tecnológica e Inovação (ABIPTI)

⁴ According to Ministério do Trabalho.

In the center of Figure 5 it is illustrated the national communication infrastructure. Besides the networking connectivity (in Brazil represented by the National Research Network – RNP), one must consider the CRIS (represented by the NISPs Portal Inovação⁵ and Plataforma Lattes⁶). The CRIS can be individual or national wide (as the ones represented in Figure 5).

Brief history of a Brazilian ST&I NISP

In Figures 6a and 6b we represent the main developments on some of the most important ST&I Brazilian CRIS.

Early periods: from paper to electronic forms

In the early stages, the main goal of public manager was to end the use of paper forms by electronic forms. From the middle 80s to the end of 90s the Brazilian S&T community received four CVs systems from two public agencies. Even though the operational processes had improved significantly from the previous, all S&T players were dissatisfied with the information system they had to use. Researchers and other individual funding candidate had to duplicate their personal data in separate systems (sometimes registering what they already had registered in other funding opportunity). S&T public managers did not have representative data from the national S&T system unless they hire additional survey studies.

Figure 6a: Brazilian CRIS Chronology – Early stages to 2004

⁵ www.portalinovacao.mct.gov.br – NISP dedicated to promote technical collaboration and innovation.

⁶ <http://lattes.cnpq.br> – dedicated to map S&T curricula, R&D groups and funding.

NISP in S&T - Plataforma Lattes

In the end of the 90s the Brazilian Council of S&T – CNPq - launched *Plataforma Lattes*, Lattes a ST&I NISP created to provide information services to its sponsor agency and to researchers, students, institutions and research groups. Its name honors the Brazilian researcher Cesar Lattes, π -meson co-discoverer. Lattes is managed by CNPq - the National Council for Science and Technology. Its development resulted from a multi-institutional collaboration research project. Figure 6a represents the e-Gov methodology and its main products and characteristics. Since 1999, Plataforma Lattes has been registering and managing ST&I information being recognized as one of the most important databases on national competences (Lane, 2010).

The first S&T information entity launched in Lattes project was the curriculum. The new CV system resulted from a poll with more than 700 researchers. More than 400 answered CNPq telling how should be a national S&T CV system. More than a 100 tested the first versions giving a grade of 4,2 on a zero up to five scale. Lattes project considered the researchers suggestions and was launched with the capability of importing data from all four electronic curricula available in the country⁷.

In this phase, as part of the e-Gov methodology, the academic group responsible for Lattes Project and CNPq representatives created a community of practice for Lattes standards. In the following years more than twenty institutions worked in the community of practice named Conscientias. The first job was to review and publicize CV Lattes as a national standard. As a result some universities created bridges among their legacy systems and CV Lattes, offering automated cvs to their researchers, facilitating their work of created an historical professional profile. The capacity of importing other electronic cv files and the services created by some universities were essential because these facts showed the researchers that Lattes was in fact a national standard that had come to stay.

In the first part of Figure 6b some of the other results of Lattes project are represented. Lattes was one of the first projects with an integrated data warehouse dedicated to S&T investment analysis. “Lattes Fomento” allows the user to check for S&T investments classified in several manners (e.g., by region, by knowledge area, by funding beneficiary) and it has been running since 2000. It is an instrument to government transparency. Its services have been used by funding candidates to check for candidate classification. Another kind of knowledge systems developed in the Lattes project are the network systems (ex. graduate courses alumni network to help course coordinators to inform CAPES – the national agency responsible for graduate course evaluation). These systems allowed the user to discover what kind of connections the S&T players have in the National S&T system (e.g., advising, collaboration, institutional networks). They were the basis for the current network analysis systems used in Lattes and in Portal Inovação.

⁷ Brazil had the following electronic forms: BCURR and Minicurriculum (from CNPq, used in all S&T individual funding programs for DOS and Windows operating systems, respectively), CNCT (from MCT, that was used to gather curricula to a particular national funding program - PADCT) and Coleta (from CAPES, that gathered data from all professors working in graduate programs).

Figure 6b: Brazilian CRIS Chronology – 1997 up to 2010.

At the bottom of Figure 6b, in the period from 2000 to 2004, two other developments are emphasized: the development of the institutional concept to Plataforma Lattes, and the creation of ScienTI Network.

Institutional Lattes Plataform

The first one was a project created to allow universities and R&D institutions to obtain all individual CVs connected to its organizations (by job, education, or address reference) and make them source to support research and administrative decision making⁸. In the following years more than a hundred institutions settled an agreement with CNPq to obtain and manage their individual CVs. This was a crucial step to start the Lattes exponential growing database⁹, because for several institutions having a CV Lattes became an administrative guideline.

ScienTI Network

The second development in Lattes project that was important to settle e-Gov guidelines was the establishment of ScienTI Network - International Information and Knowledge Network in Science, Technology and Innovation¹⁰. This network was originated from a 2000 agreement between CNPq and the Pan-American Health Organization (PAHO). The agreement combined the experiences of these organizations in the administration of information sources in ST&I. From CNPq side was Plataforma Lattes model and from PAHO was the Virtual Health Library (VHL) developed by BIREME. Lattes defined data standards and proposed systems to deal with national S&T information (curricula, research groups, institutions and projects), and VHL had established international standards and services to access to documents (digital libraries) and cooperation sources in health in Latin America and the Caribbean (Sartori and Pacheco, 2006).

⁸ Plataforma Lattes informs all users that their data is public with privacy policies. CNPq makes available only the CV public data which is combined with other information by the university systems.

⁹ From 1987 to 1999 CNPq had accumulated about 42 thousand CVs. From 1999 to 2011 this number reached the 2 million individual CVs.

¹⁰ www.scienti.net

In the end of 2002 there were eleven countries participating in ScienTI. ScienTI had four nucleus – (i) National S&T Councils; (ii) International Organizations in S&T; (iii) Academic Groups dedicated to CRIS R&D; and (iv) Other supporting organizations (including firms). Each nucleus had a complementary mission in ScienTI. The national S&T councils should establish the platforms as CNPq did in Brazil. The international organizations should promote, amplify and make use of ScienTI data as PAHO, BIREME and latter RICYT or to support ScienTI developments (as UNESCO and BID did). The academic groups should establish a technical and research network of CRIS to adapt and increase all ScienTI information systems. The fourth nucleus was established to receive other promoters interested in support ScienTI (ex. software companies offering free tools).

ScienTI network ultimate mission was to guarantee democratic access to all S&T knowledge created in its country members (Naves, 2003). This mission was pursued by the establishment of international standards, interoperability and common services to access all S&T data created in the country members (Naves, 2002).

In the following years the national S&T councils worked to establish their own CRIS, either by installing Lattes systems or by developing their own technological solutions. In 2002 there were a total of 263.500 CVs in three ScienTI countries¹¹. In 2005 this number reached the total of 682.920 curricula¹².

Although the countries had created their databases, the interoperability was still a matter of further agreement. Previous political decisions had technical and research negative impact over ScienTI. In the following years the changes in the national governments brought representatives that decided to modify ScienTI principles. The academic groups were formally expelled from the net and the next meetings were dedicated to interchange administrative experiences from the national S&T councils in dealing with operational data.

ScienTI initiative brought a set of learned lessons in international information S&T agreements. The main lesson is related to governance and sustainability. The ScienTI governance model was unable to create foundations strong enough to be immune to national political changes. As the new official representatives entered ScienTI, the agreements were reviewed without assurance that the network landmarks were not to be changed. Another problem was the sustainability model incapable to assure that all countries would have access to technological and methodological developments.

As it can be seen in Figure 6b, starting in 2004 there were other the Brazilian NISP developed after Lattes and ScienTI projects. These NISP projects have a common e-Gov methodology that was elaborated during the development of Plataforma Lattes by the academic group responsible for conceiving, researching, developing and implementing the main Lattes

¹¹ In 2002 Brazil had 248.000 Lattes CVs, Colombia had already reached 13.500 CVs and Chile started with 2 thousand CVs.

¹² In 2005 Argentina had created a database with 35.580 curricula, Brazil had reached 580.000 Lattes CVs, Colombia had a base with 40.000 curricula, Chile had 7.290 curricula, Ecuador had its first 430 curricula, Mexico had a database with 11.900 curricula, Peru had its first 2.200 curricula, Portugal, after working in its DeGois Platform reached the 4.100 curricula, and Venezuela had its first 1.420 curricula.

components. This methodology was first described in 2003 (Pacheco, 2003). In the following sections we describe the main aspects of the methodology, the characteristics of the e-Gov architectures developed under its principles and the guidelines learned from these experiences and present the other NISP projects represented in Figure 6b.

Brazilian e-Gov Methodology and Architecture

The e-Gov methodology created during the Lattes project is based on general assumptions (guidelines) about the way public data should be defined, collected, processed and distributed. These principles were gradually learned from the experience of conceiving and developing lattes architecture. They were also based on a continuous process of literature review in e-Gov and in CRIS development. In these sections we summarize the principles, the methodology and the architecture derived from its application. We also describe some e-Gov projects developed under the same instruments.

The e-Gov principles of NISP based on the Lattes e-Gov methodology

The relevance of NISP e-Gov principles is in the fact that each CRIS developed somehow represents the public authority world view. If the S&T public manager is more oriented to operational control, the CRIS will be less flexible and less transparent to the rest of the society. If the public manager considers financial sponsorship the main criteria to establish the CRIS requirements, probably the systems will treat only the government needs.

All current CRIS are based on past public management decisions. The sponsor agency must be aware that the CRIS mission, requirements, life cycle, and its connectivity to other CRIS depend upon its early project view and decisions.

In Figure 7 we list seven principles of NISP development learned from the Lattes project development and from its application to other e-Gov projects.

Figure 7: The e-Gov principles of NISP based on the Lattes e-Gov methodology.

The first principle is related to the public manager's world view. It refers to the way the decision maker sees the role of government in a national information system. In the first generation of e-government, e-Gov projects were dedicated exclusively to help government to deal with its internal processes. As a result, citizens were seen only as data providers. In order to create a NISP the government must take into account that more than gather data an e-Gov project should build a national space of information and services. Citizens should recognize the systems as useful tools not only to government but also to their own information needs. This is only possible when the public authorities acknowledge the need for meeting citizen needs as well as government requirements. This principle is related to OECD principles related to vision/political will (Figure 4). In the case of Lattes, an example of this view was the development of several external CV report models. This was not a CNPq necessity but it was a complain that researchers had done about the previous systems.

The second principle is related to the NISP mission. The public manager world view is generally translated into a system mission. When the task is to fulfill operational government needs the mission will be related to transactional systems. But when the public authorities acknowledge the importance of promote information society, the NISP will be a truly platform of systems that deal not only with operational but also with strategic processes. This principle is related to the "customer focus" OECD guideline (Figure 4). In the case of Plataforma Lattes, CNPq authorities required not only new electronic forms to deal with the Council's matters but demand for a national space of S&T information.

The third principle is related to NISP data requirement. It is a direct consequence of the first two. Data requirements are map from user interviews and from the research about the user needs. In order to be strategic and systemic to all players related to its domain, a NISP project must take into account not only government data requirement but also the other ST&I player needs. This entails a responsibility not only with requirement but also with maintain the services even when there are not dedicated to government use. This principle is related to the responsibility OECD guidelines (Figure 4). In the case of Plataforma Lattes there were several systems created to offer services to the S&T community. An example was the alumni networking systems, created to help graduate course coordinators to answer CAPES about their former students.

The fourth principle is another consequence of the other three: the system ownership. In order to have a NISP the public authorities sponsoring the project should aim to create a public domain platform rather than governmental asset. The notion of public domain in Lattes can be exemplified by the institutional Lattes project and by the CNPq policy in offering Lattes database to other agencies.

The fifth principle is related to the system life cycle. E-Gov projects can be created to deal with particular needs for data management or to establish a continuous evolving information platform. The first approach is chipper and faster but has a shorter life cycle. This principle is related to OECD responsibility guidelines (Figure 4). In the case of Lattes, the Platform has completed eleven years with a continuous evolution program, based on the same set of original premises.

The sixth principle is connectivity. It is related to other aspect of how requirements are settled. An e-Gov project can be designed to run isolated from information systems outside the sponsor agency. At first this will save time because all decisions can be made without further agreements. Issues such as data standards and interoperability will not be project concerns. However, in the future there might be difficulties to connect the CRIS with other initiatives and, more importantly, an isolated development might be contradictory to S&T standards. A NISP should foresee standards and interoperability resources since the beginning of its project. This principle is related to OECD guidelines on vision/political will (integration) and on common frameworks/co-operation (Figure 4). In the case of Lattes, two initiatives established the basis for Lattes connectivity: the publication of Lattes data in standard format (XML) and the establishment of a community of practice with representatives from more than 20 important institutions of the national ST&I system to keep and improve the original standards. Even when this community was disabled by CNPq after 2004, its work established the culture and the practice for Lattes connectivity.

The last principle learned from the Lattes project is related the methodology behind its development. Since CRIS are information systems, it is reasonable to suppose that software engineering alone is sufficient to deal with all project challenges. However, the task of including not only information but also knowledge management requires a multidisciplinary team configuration. Besides e-government, a R&D NISP project demands knowledge from public management, information society, knowledge engineering, strategic planning and other areas. Rather than an ordinary software engineering project a NISP in R&D is an open space for research, innovation and development in all these areas. During the first six years Lattes was a R&D project hired from CNPq to an academic group responsible for researching, modeling, developing and implementing Lattes solutions in a partnership with the CNPq professionals (from management and information technology areas).

All these principles were established after a sequence of projects based on the e-Gov methodology created to conduct Lattes projects. In the next sections we present such methodology and the main characteristics of its resultant e-Gov architecture.

The e-Gov Methodology for NISP

A methodology to develop technology consists of a number of elements that establish five building blocks, organized as hierarchical layers - (i) world view; (ii) theory; (iii) methods; (iv) tools; and (v) use. The first layer is based on guidelines, principles based on lessons learned from previous projects that need to be grounded in theory, methods, tools and practical case studies (Schreiber, et. al. 2000).

In the previous section we described the e-Gov principles learned from Lattes project. They can be seen as the world view of the way Lattes project e-Gov researchers see the way a NISP should be designed and developed. According to these principles an e-Gov project to establish a NISP considers the processes of designing, developing, using and revising a continuous flow of activities. This virtuous cycle is represented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: e-Gov methodology developed during the Lattes project.

Source: Pacheco, 2003

According to Figure 8 there is an interactive cycle between design and operation. The cycle frequency is determined by the information demands. The e-Gov operation phase brings knowledge to the project that restart the cycle from the requirement definition. This restart can be fired by the interaction at the level of the tasks of each phase (Pacheco, 2003).

In the design phase the project starts from the definition of the requirements, identifying which of the ST&I players will be beneficiary and which information services will be developed. These requirements are input elements to e-Gov planning when elements such as the information flow, IT facilities and the e-Gov life cycle are determined. As a supporting activity to planning there is need for a related project study, particularly the ones that deal with correspondent S&T entities. The creation of communities of practice intends to promote collaborative work among stakeholders that represent users or data standards definers. The next phase will be dedicated to development and deployment of the e-Gov solutions. The last design task will be the e-Gov management and maintenance, when both technological and methodological components are managed. This includes user relationship management and monitoring the use of the e-Gov facilities (Pacheco, 2003).

In the operational phase includes tasks that deal with the relation between the users and the e-Gov technological components. In the user interaction management the government should establish mechanisms to track and evaluate users' opinion and critics to the services. The continuous use of the e-Gov platform will create and update the information sources. They are inputs and outputs to the e-services offered to the S&T community. The project should also include communities of practice where users will take the e-Gov platform to levels higher than

the services designed to gather data from users to manage government needs. The last stage of the operational phase is characterized by the knowledge services, the set of services designed to derive knowledge from the e-Gov data sources. Knowledge services are achieved by business intelligence, knowledge engineering, ontology, network analysis, and other knowledge technologies (Pacheco, 2003).

In Brazil the cycle defined by the design and operation phases represented in Figure 8 was a methodological reference to R&D NISP projects in different domains. The results have shown that when principles or guidelines described above are not followed (or are abandoned in the following years) the e-Gov architecture life cycle is decreased. There is a direct relation between the e-Gov methodology and the resultant e-Gov architecture developed. In the following section we show the structure and main components of the e-Gov architectures resulted from the application of the e-Gov methodology.

The e-Gov Architecture for NISP

An e-Gov architecture is a conceptual framework describing all technical components and correspondent relationships. The Lattes e-Gov architecture was also described as SCienTI e-Gov architecture (Pacheco et. al, 2006). In Figure 9 we present the e-Gov architecture created to Lattes and other Brazilian ST&I NISP.

Figure 9: Lattes and SCienTI e-Gov architecture

Source: Pacheco, 2003

The Lattes e-Gov architecture is a four-layer technological structure. The bottom layer comprises the ST&I information entities managed by the NISP. In the case of Lattes, this layer has curricula, R&D groups, projects, and institutions. Each entity is standardized and its data format is made public available so other CRIS developers can use it as a reference to establish data models. One of the main principles in Lattes project was the acknowledgement that metadata redundancy is unavoidable on a NISP (Pacheco, et. al, 2006). For instance, theoretically a publication should not have its metadata replicated in different registers. In practice this would make the authors' individual cvs dependent from a centralized publication

database. The problem is that an author cannot depend on third parties when he or she wants to update his or her cv in order to send a fund proposal.

The second layer of the architecture contains the information systems (or CRIS) that manage the primary data sources. This layer has also the secondary sources – data marts - created from the extraction, transportation and loading of the operational data. These data marts are the sources to information and knowledge systems located in the third and fourth layers, respectively. Besides transactional information systems and data marts, the second layer can also include community of practices, as the e-Gov methodology prescribes in its design and operational phases.

The third layer represents the information systems created to support decision making in the NISP domain. The secondary sources are inputs to web portals, search engine systems, business intelligence systems, and other decision support systems available. While the second layer has information systems that manage the primary data, the third layer has information systems that deal with secondary sources. This layer has also web services to interoperate its services with the other layers or with systems outside the NISP architecture.

The fourth layer is composed by knowledge systems such as knowledge discovery, networking analysis, and intelligent agents. Their mission is to explore both primary and secondary data sources in order to create additional information and knowledge useful to decision making processes. This layer is designed to help knowledge intensive tasks such as impact analysis and foresight in the domain of the NISP. Its knowledge systems are dependent on the data quality and completeness derived from the previous layers.

In the last ten years the Lattes/ScienTI e-Gov methodology was applied to several NISP projects in domains such as health surveillance, higher education, environment and innovation. In the next section we present these projects.

Other e-Gov projects based on the same methodology

About five years after Lattes being launched in 1999, its outcomes started to be recognized in the national information scenario in Brazil. In this period other public managers realized that a NISP could have similar results on their domain.

NISP in Higher Education – Portal SINAES and BASis

The first NISP project was in the higher education domain. The National Institute for Studies and Research on Education - INEP¹³ is responsible for evaluating institutions and undergraduate courses in Brazil. One of the main problems in this process is to settle an appropriate evaluation committee. When visiting a higher education institution or a graduate course the INEP evaluators must have experience, education and affinity with the correspondent field.

¹³ INEP - Instituto Nacional de Estudos e Pesquisas Educacionais Anísio Teixeira.

In 2006 INEP decided to change the evaluator database using CV Lattes as the reference to evaluate the evaluator candidates. INEP and CNPq made an agreement and all Lattes CVs were mirror at INEP computer server. The Institute began to use Lattes CV integrated to other SINAES systems. More than 20 thousand candidates applied to INEP in order to be a course or an institutional evaluator. All courses councils, professional and scientific entities were invited to indicate candidates.

An e-Gov architecture called “Portal SINAES” was developed to INEP based on the Lattes e-Gov methodology. Its mission was to update the data about all professors and courses in Brazil and to support the evaluator selection process. In order to select the evaluators SINAES architecture had a system called BASIs. This system received Lattes CV complemented with additional data required to candidates and calculated a rank based on 41 indicators in five categories – experience on academic management, academic competence, scientific competence, technological competence, and networking. BASIs had different grades to each category and could cross the cv data of each candidate, calculating an index to evaluation profile. In the end INEP renewed its database selecting 4.495 candidates for institutional evaluation and 8.992 for course evaluations. The database was increased and qualified by a democratic and open process that helped the national evaluation system for undergraduate courses and higher education institutions (Ristoff, et. al. 2006)¹⁴.

NISP of Health Surveillance competencies - DCVISA

By the same time a NISP was being elaborated to higher education evaluation, the National Agency on Health Surveillance (ANVISA) was looking for a solution for a challenge problem: how to map and find national competences in all areas related to health surveillance? The answer came once again from Plataforma Lattes. As INEP, ANVISA made an agreement with CNPq to obtain Lattes mirror. The original data were increased by additional data about health surveillance and a new expertise data repository was built. In Figure 10 there is a schematic view of how researchers and professionals inform ANVISA about their expertise and interests in health surveillance related topics. The DCVISA database is composed by Lattes curriculum added with health surveillance profiles and by the content created by the communities of practice in ANVISA. Besides this, ANVISA has access to information and knowledge systems designed to support the agency in some strategic tasks such as expertise location and communication.

¹⁴ BASIs and SINAES Project were honored with the World Bank international prize in regional statistical innovation.

Figure 10: DCVISA data flow and main information services.

NISP on education in environment management – Portal SIBEA

In 2004 the Ministry of Environment had concluded an analysis about one of its main information projects: SIBEA – Information System for Environmental Education (EE), a web portal developed in partnership with other public agencies, non-governmental organizations, and environmental information networks. SIBEA mission is to manage information on environmental education allowing planning, promotion, coordination and dissemination of educational activities. The analysis had concluded that SIBEA was technically founded in public non-numerical information storage grounds. It allowed SIBEA to publish documents but it lacked a systematic architecture, making difficult to add new services and new players related with environmental education.

From 2005 to 2007 the e-Gov methodology developed in Lattes project was applied to develop a new SIBEA architecture. Figure 11 depicts the SIBEA data flow and the main services offered to all environmental education stakeholders. In SIBEA Lattes curricula are the basis for an EE competence database. The Environment Ministry and CNPq set an agreement so the Lattes database can be mirrored in SINIMA data space¹⁵. Each EE stakeholder (educators, institutional representatives, environmental network members, and others) has a specific information space to access SIBEA Portal. Once their Lattes curricula are imported to SINIMA, the users can add additional data such as their environmental profile, pedagogical documents, and institutional data. They also access information services, such as search for EE profiles, indicators about EE, and EE network maps.

¹⁵ SINIMA – Sistema Nacional de Informações em Meio Ambiente – or National information System in Environment, defined and maintained by MMA.

Figure 11: Mains services and flow information in SIBEA e-Gov architecture.

Currently SIBEA Portal is still on the air but in the last four years did not receive further investments to advance in its e-Gov architecture. Nevertheless, since it was grounded on an e-Gov methodology its services are still useful to EE stakeholders. An interesting investigation on this project would to check whether the further investments were stopped because of budget constraints or because the new public managers in Environmental Ministry did not consider SIBEA a priority as the previous ones did. The first cause is related to the OECD financing principle and the second with OECD political will, that as we see before (Figure 4) are essential to a continuous successful e-Gov initiative.

NISP on technological collaboration and innovation – *Portal Inovação*

The last example of NISP developed according to the e-Gov methodology applied in Lattes project is *Portal Inovação*, a national web space designed to promote cooperation and offer information services to all innovation players of the Brazilian National ST&I system. Launched in 2005, the Portal is sponsored by Ministry of Science and Technology (MCT), conceptualized by the Center for Strategic Studies and Management in Science, Technology and Innovation (CGEE), developed by Instituto Stela, a no-for profit private research institute founded by Lattes creators, and operated by the Brazilian Agency for Industrial Development (ABDI).

In this case, it seems interesting to notice that its genesis and further developments exemplify some of OECD guidelines for e-Gov success.

In 2004 Brazil was about to regulate the National Innovation Law. One of the main concerns at MCT was to promote technological cooperation among academic and industrial sectors. There was a consensus about the fact that although research productivity had increased significantly in Brazil, it was mainly confined to public academic environment. There was (and still is) a gap between research and innovation outputs.

In the first semester of 2004, the MCT executive vice-minister was presented to INVENTEC, a regional information ST&I system developed in Bahia to map innovation demands and

offerings. The demands were defined by interviewing firms CEOs and the offerings by visiting academic research group competences and facilities. This map was used with relative success to approximate research offerings and industrial demands. In the following months the vice-minister asked CGEE to create a Web Portal that could take INVENTEC results to a national level.

As a result CGEE, a group of innovation experts, and the Lattes development group worked to define the main characteristics of the national cooperation space demanded by MCT. This group defined Portal Inovação mission as to be a web space for technological cooperation among innovation players. As such, the Portal should have access to the national offerings, demands and competences in ST&I.

Regarding competences, at this time Lattes had already become a national reference. CGEE and CNPq worked on an agreement to allow the use of Lattes data – curricula and R&D groups – as one of the Portal Inovação database on ST&I competences. It was agreed however that the language and services to deal and show competences should be different from the correspondent services in Plataforma Lattes. The project team defined the language by which Lattes data should be presented to firm managers and other innovation stakeholders. In Figure 12 there is an example of how the same Lattes curriculum is translated into a technological or into an academic format. The first format was determined by asking some firm’s owner about which profile data are important to decide whether they would invite the researcher for a cooperation or not. The academic résumé was defined on a previous research that analyzed more than 200 résumés presented by researchers on their personal profiles (Martins, 2004).

Figure 12: Technological (a) and academic résumés (b) automatic generated by Portal Inovação knowledge systems (obs.: translated here from the original Portuguese texts)

Besides the difference in the way Lattes data should be presented in Portal Inovação, another issue was how to reveal demands and offerings from firms. The strategy was to interview about 20 firm representatives. The challenge was to set a CRIS that at the same time acquire relevant information about demands and offerings and does not annoy the user with a long data requests. This was done by researching similar CRIS (with data about firms) and by testing eleven different data sets with firm representatives. By the end of 2004 Portal Inovação had defined its mission and information entities (expert and firm profiles, firm demands and offerings, and cooperation messages). During this first phase CGEE invited representative from

all kinds of innovation players¹⁶, as suggested by the OECD inter-agency collaboration principle (Figure 4) and as recommended by the connectivity Lattes e-Gov methodology principle (Figure 7).

In 2005 and 2006 Portal Inovação went through its second phase. It was during this period that the e-Gov architecture was designed, developed and implemented. The data infrastructure included Lattes databases by an automatically updated mirror. An interesting development was the inclusion of Science, Technology and Innovation Institutions (STI), their research units and innovation offices as explicit innovation players at the Portal.

In the third phase (2007-2008) there was a need to add more innovation players (innovation agents) and more information services (strategic indicators, communities of practice, networking and topic maps). Another demand was to open the e-Gov architecture to be possible creating thematic or sectorial subportals and to connect Portal Inovação with others by means of interoperability. In this period Portal Inovação received its first subportal created to small and medium firms, later increased to be the national portal to evaluate incubators, science parks and technological based firms (Portal SAPI¹⁷).

In this fourth period (2009 up to now), Portal Inovação has been increased by adding new databases – the national database on intellectual property rights by INPI¹⁸ - by interoperability services and by connection with other national ST&I information initiatives. The first was done in 2009 when Portal Inovação helped a FINEP national innovation funding – PRIME, First Firm Program. In this last case, due to the way Portal Inovação architecture was designed, it was possible to integrate its services to an operational process, offering FINEP for the first time in its history a strategic information panel to follow its funding program. Another development from this period is the thematic Portal on Biotechnology, designed in cooperation with the MDIC - Ministry of Development, Industry and Foreign Trade.

In Figure 13 we present the Portal Inovação elements described before. Portal Inovação has two sets of databases. The first are the information sources created by the own Portal operation, and includes innovation demands, offerings, competences, and content managed by ABDI. The second set is composed by imported databases from other CRIS (i.e., Plataforma Lattes and INPI databases), and by databases created by sectorial (SAPI from ANPROTEC or PRIME from FINEP) or thematic subportals (Biotechnology from MDIC).

¹⁶ Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq); Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos (FINEP); Serviço Brasileiro de Apoio às Micro e Pequenas Empresas (SEBRAE); Confederação Nacional da Indústria (CNI); Instituto Euvaldo Lodi (IEL); Associação Nacional de Pesquisa, Desenvolvimento e Engenharia das Empresas Inovadoras (ANPEI); Núcleo de Assuntos Estratégicos (NAE) – Presidência da República; Fórum de Pró-Reitores de Pesquisa e Pós-Graduação (FOPROP); Instituto Nacional de Metrologia, Normalização e Qualidade Industrial (INMETRO); Agência Brasileira de Desenvolvimento Industrial (ABDI); Associação Nacional de Entidades Promotoras de Empreendimentos Inovadores (ANPROTEC).

¹⁷ www.portalinovacao.mct.gov.br/sapi

¹⁸ INPI – Instituto Nacional de Propriedade Industrial

Figure 13: General view of Portal Inovação components.

The e-Gov architecture created to Portal Inovação, represented in Figure 13, made possible to use Lattes database in both academic and business oriented languages, to manage data from all ST&I players (e.g. demands and offers; expert, firms and institutional profiles), and to provide content, communication and other information services. It has a flexible platform that allows for distinct innovation spaces (as SAPI, PRIME and Biotechnology) and for integration and interoperability with several national databases related to innovation (Lattes - CNPq, intellectual property – INPI, etc.).

We described some NISP developed in Brazil with Lattes e-Gov methodology. These projects have established several CRIS in the Brazilian ST&I information scenario. These CRIS have created databases and knowledge systems that can help in issues related to ST&I evaluation and planning. In the next section we discuss some examples of how these elements were combined to study ST&I in Brazil.

HOW NISP CAN HELP TO EVALUATE ST&I

The main issue in this article is whether ST&I NISP can face the difficulties associated to research impact analysis. In the case of the NISP described before there were some case studies that help to notice how ST&I data can be treated in different decision making situations. We present three of these cases in the following sections.

Case 1: Brazilian research on climate

The first case study is related to SIBEA system. One of the purposes of this system was to establish a national competence database on environment field. When SIBEA database was established with a mirror of Lattes CVs database, there were questions such as: how would be the research on climate (“clima”) in the country? Which would be the topics associated with this research field? What could be concluded from such analysis?

In Figure 14 we depict the result of a knowledge system applied to CV Lattes technology in order to study such issues. The process consisted of separating all CVs that have the word “clima” in their knowledge profiles. With all these CVs each word co-occurrence is annotated. After checking the co-occurrences, the most frequent are connected and mapped in a same figure, as presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Topic map analysis about research on “clima” in Brazil.

According Figure 14, the research on “clima” in Brazil allows to identify the following thematic clusters: “mudanças climáticas”, “Bioclimatologia”, “clima urbano”, “ensino da climatologia”, “microclima”, and “Climatic Changes”. Each cluster is customized according to the most

frequent correspondent research subject. It is interesting to notice the difference between the clusters “Mudanças climáticas” and “Climatic Changes”. Even though they are the same expression for Portuguese and English, respectively, the correspondent frequent terms are not. This means that the Brazilian researchers work on different topics when publishing outside the country compared to national publications. In the Brazilian publication the researchers are concerned with education (“clima e ensino”, “teoria e prática”), while when publishing outside the country the main concerns are related to subject as “rainfall”, and “climatology”.

Knowledge topic maps can help to evaluate national (or regional or institutional) research profile. A useful tool appears when the topic maps are compared along different periods of time. Changes in the topic co-occurrence or the appearance of new topics on the map can be depicted and analyzed. It is important to notice that topic analysis does not depend on the existence of NISP. However, if the topic analysis is a tool of the NISP architecture, such studies will be easily created.

Case 2: Brazilian research on science and mechanical engineering

The second case study was established to analyze the research profile on mechanical science and engineering (Pacheco, et. al., 2007b). In this study the goal was to analyze the national research on mechanical science and mechanical engineering and present this profile at an international conference in mechanical engineering. In Figura 15 we present one of the topic maps created to analyze the research on these areas in Brazil.

Figure 15: Topic map analysis about research on science and mechanical engineering in Brazil (subject: manufacturing).

The process of creating the topic maps was similar to the one applied in the environment study. However, this time the researchers started from topics used by reviewers when they established the tracks for a national conference on the studied areas. The curricula analyzed were from researchers with a PhD degree in mechanical engineering. The study created 16 topic maps (the same number of tracks on the national conference on mechanical engineering). In Figure 15 it is showed the map about the research on “manufacturing”. It can be seen that the research in Brazil on “manufacturing” is related to “CAM”, “CAAP”, “CAD”, “Fabrication” (“Fabricação”), “Tools” (“Ferramentas”) - which is related to “Machines” (“Máquinas”), and “Conformation” (“Conformação”) - which is related to “Welding” (“Sondagem”).

An expert on mechanical science that studied the topic maps created has indicated some interesting characteristics about the research in the area in Brazil (Pacheco, et. al, 2007b). One of the conclusions is that the studied reveal that there are similarities and topic co-occurrence among different conference tracks. This might be considered by conference responsible because would facilitate paper submissions to the authors (since track overlaps would be avoided).

Case 3: Searching for experts in health research

The last example of how ST&I data from a NISP can help decision making came from another real case: MERCK & Co. Inc., a worldwide healthcare company. In 2009 MERCK had announced its main research interest in health (Figure 16).

Atherosclerosis and Cardiovascular Diseases	<p>EMBRACING PARTNERSHIPS</p> <p>Atherosclerosis and Cardiovascular Diseases</p> <p>LIPIDS / METABOLIC SYNDROME</p> <p>Areas of Interest:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel LDL- and triglyceride-lowering (apoB-lowering) therapies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – eg. cholesterol absorption inhibitors and agents that target PCSK9 – Agents with additional effect on glucose, body weight, and / or HDL • HDL-raising therapies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Acute HDL-mimetic (or apoA-I mimetics) therapy for high-risk patients – Oral compounds, with known mechanism of action, that increase HDL-C or apoA-I levels <p>Technology / Methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cell-based screening assays for new target identification in hepatocytes, adipocytes and enterocytes • Methods, biomarkers, or platforms to assess antiatherogenic properties of HDL or other lipoproteins • Acute methods to assess cholesterol transport in humans (especially reverse cholesterol transport), including imaging and kinetic models • Acute methods to assess gut lipoprotein production in animals and / or humans • Platform technologies for identifying novel lipid targets • GWAS and other genomic datasets from cohorts with well-phenotyped lipid and metabolic end points • Biomarkers of patient subtypes 	<p>Not Interested in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-selective ACAT inhibitors • Triglyceride-lowering therapies with no other benefit • Fibrates or other PPAR-alpha agonists • Early-stage PPAR-delta agonists • Fish oil • Nutraceuticals • In vitro reverse cholesterol transport assays
<p>Lipids / Metabolic Syndrome.....</p> <p>Vascular Wall</p> <p>Hypertension / Cardiovascular</p> <p>Biologics</p> <p>Follow-on Biologics.....</p> <p>Novel Biologics.....</p> <p>Biologic Technologies.....</p> <p>Bone, Respiratory, Immunology, and Endocrine</p> <p>Anemia.....</p> <p>Arthritis and Immune-Based Diseases</p> <p>Asthma / COPD.....</p> <p>Bone</p> <p>Sarcopenia</p> <p>Urology</p> <p>Diabetes and Obesity</p> <p>Diabetes.....</p> <p>Obesity.....</p> <p>Infectious Diseases and Vaccines</p> <p>Antibacterials.....</p> <p>Antifungals.....</p> <p>Antivirals – HIV</p> <p>Antivirals – HCV</p> <p>Antivirals – Other Interests.....</p> <p>Antiviral and Anti-infective Technologies.....</p> <p>Vaccines.....</p>		

Figure 16: Areas of MERCK Labs interest in research collaboration.

country. If pictures like that could be taken during different periods of time, an analyst can check for the research profile evolution in certain area. This could be used, for instance, to compare goals and priorities of funding programs with knowledge maps built before and long after the programs to check for (in) evolutions or funding goal achievements.

Case 4: Helping a national fund program to evaluate candidates

Another case in the strategic use of the national information on ST&I in Brazil was conducted in 2008. The S&T Ministry and CNPq had launched a national fund program for research called INCT – *Institutos Nacionais de Ciência e Tecnologia*. INCT was a national funding program to create national institutes as research networks working in areas considered strategic to Brazil. One of the goals is to “promote the articulation and integration, through the establishment of networks among the best research groups and individuals in the country, in priority areas” (INCT, 2011).

Contrarily to other funding programs that deal with individual, project team or organizational proposals, INCT was about to evaluate research networks. This brought new concerns to the program evaluation process. Issues such as: (i) How they can act as a network, taking research beyond geographical borders? (ii) Do the proponents already work as a network or they designed the network by the time the INCT call for proposal was announced?; or How to evaluate the impact of INCT program on the networking activities?

By the time the evaluators were analyzing the proposals for INCT, CNPq asked CGEE to check whether the knowledge systems available in Portal Inovação architecture could help to evaluate the INCT candidates’ networking activities. In Figure 19 we present an example of the studies developed in order to help to evaluate networking activities. For each proposal the evaluators had access to the number of previous co-authorships, advising, project co-participation, and committee co-participation among the network members. All these relations were also graphically presented, so the evaluators could check visually how was the intensity of each networking activity among researchers of a particular fund proposal.

Data obtained from Lattes Platform CVs
 Analysis done by services provided by Innovation Portal

Figure 19: Portal Inovação Knowledge systems applied to support proposal evaluation of a national funding program for research networks.

The analyses done by the time the proposals were being evaluated helped to check the level of relationships among participants in each candidate network. Once the program began, the issue became to check whether the funded networks were increasing the initial level of relationships. Figures 20 and 21 show respectively a positive and a negative answer for this question.

In Figure 20, the first snapshot is about co-authorship relations in 2008 and the second is the level of relations in 2011. It can be seen that some researchers have increased significantly the number of relations (ex. a researcher called "Raul" did not have any relation with the others in 2008 but had 22 relations in 2011).

Figure 20: Example a network that has increased the number of relationships after being funded

In Figure 21, it can be seen that the network has kept the same clusters of research collaboration that it did before being funded. There still a lot of researchers that do not publish with the other network members.

Figure 20: Example a network that did not increased the number of relationships after being funded

CONCLUSIONS

In this article we addressed the role of CRIS on Science, Technology and Innovation systems. These information systems create and deal with R&D data that should be useful not only to operational but also to strategic decision making. However, ST&I decision makers and analysts have been facing troubles in finding useful data to strategic planning and analysis. This problem is even worst when the analyses are about a national (or regional) ST&I systems, because the data should represent activities from all innovation stakeholders.

This problem has its roots on the following CRIS development characteristics: (i) too narrowed views about the impact of each CRIS on a national platform of systems; (ii) information systems designed to manage specific and operational tasks; (iii) data and services requirements defined only by part of the interested stakeholders; (iv) few inter-agencies collaboration, creating redundancy and disaggregated data; and (iv) the lack of systematic e-Gov methodology.

Actually, every CRIS project is an element of a ST&I NISP. If their development lack e-Gov methodology and good practices, it will be difficult to integrate CRIS and, particularly, to create data useful to strategic analysis.

In this article we showed some Brazilian experiences in ST&I NISP development. We showed that when CRIS is treated as an e-Gov project, there will be a better chance to create ST&I NISP (such as Plataforma Lattes and Portal Inovação). In this case, useful data will not only be available, but it will also be possible to apply knowledge systems to CRIS databases, providing new information to strategic ST&I decision making processes.

In conclusion, in order to be useful to further strategic ST&I analysis, a CRIS project should: (i) apply e-Gov methodology; (ii) include strategic issues as initial requirements; (iii) apply knowledge systems to deal with CRIS and related data (ex. web documents); and (iv) involve experts in the data analysis process. The two first guidelines are about new (ore renewed) CRIS projects and the other two can be considered even when there is data from isolated CRIS or from unstructured information sources. Knowledge systems and expert analysis can be applied over web data, for instance. However, when a NISP is available the analysis will be significantly better in terms of amplitude and context.

Obviously not all strategic studies can be supported by data CRIS analysis, but most of them can be if these guidelines are followed in information systems projects. Public managers, software engineers and all ST&I stakeholders should be aware of the impact of their isolated decisions on the national (regional) view of ST&I processes, services and data. A decision made today about how to develop an information system will impact not only the process being supported but the whole NISP (especially when the system is public).

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